

Scientific article

Wind farm project valuation under revenue-driven farm control considering life time extension

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Abstract: *Wind farm operation increasingly requires integrated assessment methods that account for both economic performance and structural lifetime. This paper presents WINPACT, a modular impact-assessment framework that links wake-aware wind-farm response modeling and surrogate-based turbine load prediction with fatigue accumulation, lifetime extension, and techno-economic valuation. The framework is demonstrated using a case study of the Hollandse Kust Noord wind farm, in which a revenue-triggered shutdown strategy curtails production when projected 10-minute farm revenue falls below a defined threshold. Technical impacts are quantified in terms of start-stop frequency, idling time, fatigue damage, and potential lifetime extension under alternative assumptions about non-normal operating loads, and these results are propagated through the economic toolchain to evaluate NPV and LCOE under different revenue schemes. Under the investigated assumptions, the strategy leads to substantial increases in net present value and reductions in the levelized cost of electricity, demonstrating the potential of revenue-driven farm control to enhance the long-term economic performance of offshore wind projects.*

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